

A DECONVOLUTION METHOD FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF DISTRIBUTED SOURCES VIA LINEAR PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with high resolution bearing estimation in urban radiocommunication scenarii. Indeed, in such environments, scatterers local to the emitter engender diffuse paths that deteriorate the performances of conventional subspace-based algorithms. A deconvolution technique, involving Linear Prediction methods, is designed to characterize so called distributed sources by returning the mean angle and the angular spreading of the signal angular power density. Two ways of implementation are proposed in two extreme cases of diffuse paths correlations. Simulation results show that this proposed method provides satisfying results compared to the Cramer Rao-Bound and moreover outperform more famous subspace-based algorithms.

1. INTRODUCTION

The improvement of base station spectrum efficiency is a crucial point since the number of mobile subscribers keeps on increasing. By the use of the spatial dimension, research in signal array processing appears as a good way to get a better signal to interference ratio in radiocommunication and could then enable spectrum reuse between adjacent cells [1]. Indeed, the use of the spatial dimension could allow a better estimation of the propagation channel parameters, that adaptative antennas exploit to perform an optimal information transmission.

Precisely, this article focuses on the location problem, for which numerous High Resolution (HR) array processing methods and especially subspace-based methods have been elaborated. These latter produce efficient bearing estimators but very sensitive to model error. Now, recent studies in urban wireless communications underscored an angular spreading of the signals reaching the base station antenna array, due to scatterers local to the emitter. In this case, subspace-based methods provide disappointing results, as they rely on the point source model hypothesis.

Many authors [2],[3] proposed subspace-based algorithms generalized to the case of such distributed sources, that outperform the conventional ones. In particular, S. Valaee and B. Champagne have introduced in [4] a pro-

cessing for two scattered sources models, according to whether the impinging diffuse paths are coherently distributed or not. These two models are considered in this paper in section 2 and the use of Linear Prediction is motivated in both cases.

In section 3, this work proposes a new HR algorithm involving the deconvolution of a Linear Prediction method, first introduced in [5], by minimizing a relative error criterion. In section 4, the deconvolution principle is presented and illustrated, and two implementations are derived. The performances of both methods are evaluated and compared in the case of two extreme diffuse propagation conditions; they are also compared to subspace-based methods, to the Maximum Likelihood statistical estimator and to the Cramer-Rao bound. A special attention is paid to the Tuft-Kumaresan method to put the link between subspace-based methods and Linear prediction ones, which seems to be more robust to model mismatching.

2. MODELS FOR SCATTERED SOURCES

2.1. Previously proposed models

Let's consider a single distributed source, with wavefield impinging on an antenna array of N sensors. The discrete time complex envelope of the received snapshot vector may be modeled as [4]:

$$\mathbf{x} = \int_{-\pi/2}^{+\pi/2} \mathbf{a}(\theta) s(\theta; \alpha_0) d\theta + \mathbf{n}$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\theta)$ is the $N \times 1$ location vector of the array, $s(\theta; \alpha_0)$ is the random angular signal density of the source in the direction θ and $\alpha_0 = (\theta, \sigma_\theta)$ is the associated unknown parameter vector, here containing the nominal direction of arrival θ and the standard deviation of the angular distribution σ_θ . $\mathbf{n}$ is the $N \times 1$ additive noise vector. Assuming that the signal and the noise are uncorrelated, the noise-free correlation matrix of the observation vector $\mathbf{x}$ is given by

$$\mathbf{R}_s(\alpha_0) = \int_{-\pi/2}^{+\pi/2} \int_{-\pi/2}^{+\pi/2} \mathbf{a}(\theta) p(\theta, \theta'; \alpha_0) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta') d\theta d\theta'$$

where $p(\theta, \theta', \alpha_0) = E[s(\theta; \alpha_0) s^*(\theta'; \alpha_0)]$ is called the angular cross correlation kernel and can be determined by considering the correlation between the different diffuse paths, that depends on the environment inducing the scattering.

2.2. Application to Linear Prediction

Concerning the spatial series used in Array Processing, Linear Prediction methods can be legitimately applied only in the case of uniform linear arrays and with stationary signals as the covariance matrix $\mathbf{R}_x = \mathbf{R}_s + \sigma^2 I$ is then Toeplitz. But as explained in the previous section, in the case of distributed sources, the diffuse paths highlighting the array are more or less correlated, thus modifying the structure of $\mathbf{R}_x$. In this article two extreme cases of propagation are considered referring to [4]:

- Incoherently Distributed sources :

The impinging rays are totally uncorrelated. The noise-free array correlation matrix is thus shown as

$$\mathbf{R}_s(\alpha_0) = \int_{-\pi/2}^{+\pi/2} \mathbf{a}(\theta) p(\theta; \alpha_0) \mathbf{a}^H(\theta) d\theta$$

It must be underscored that, in this case, the source subspace can still be defined even if the signal components invade the whole space, as almost all of the signal energy is confined into a lower-dimensional subspace. It is the only case where $\mathbf{R}_x$ is Toeplitz. We will call this case the **stationary case** as the array output is a stationary spatial serie.

- Coherently Distributed sources :

The signals arriving from different rays are coherent and $s(\theta; \alpha_0) = \gamma \cdot g(\theta; \alpha_0)$ where $g(\theta; \alpha_0)$ is called the deterministic angular signal density. The angular power density of the source can thus be written

$$p(\theta; \alpha_0) = \eta \cdot g(\theta; \alpha_0) g^*(\theta; \alpha_0)$$

with $\eta = E[\gamma\gamma^*]$. In this case, the dimension of the signal subspace is $\dim(\mathbf{E}s) = 1$. This case will be called the **non stationary case** as the array output loses its stationarity property due to the diffuse correlated paths. The use of algorithms based on the minimization of the prediction error can however still be used whatever the type of propagation.

In practice the intermediate situation occurs oftently, that corresponds to the case where the rays of signal arriving from different angles are partially correlated. The partially correlated signal could be localized using the same method as the CD signal provided that the number of sensors is larger than $\dim(\mathbf{E}s)$.

Figure 1: Iterative deconvolution principle

3. LINEAR PREDICTION METHODS FOR STATIONNARY SIGNALS

3.1. DECONVOLUTION PRINCIPLE

Let's note $S_{\alpha_0}(\nu)$ the true gaussian power spectrum and $S_{\mathbf{h}_0}(\nu)$ the auto-regressive spectrum obtained by a classical Levinson algorithm from the array output. In [5], the relative estimation criterion corresponding to the Linear Prediction method has been used as a key point for deconvolution:

$$F(\alpha, \mathbf{h}_0) = \int \left| \frac{H_{\mathbf{h}_0}(\nu) - H_{\alpha}(\nu)}{H_{\alpha}(\nu)} \right|^2 d\nu \quad (1)$$

$H_{\mathbf{h}_0}(\nu)$ (resp. $H_{\alpha}(\nu)$) stands for the spectral factorization of the corresponding angular power spectra $S_{\mathbf{h}_0}(\nu)$ (resp. $S_{\alpha}(\nu)$). In the sense of this criterion, the candidate spectra, parameterized by α , will iteratively fit the best to the shape of the true spectrum parameterized by α_0 . Figure 1 illustrates how, from a candidate spectrum initialized in $\alpha = (3^\circ, 3^\circ)$, the candidate spectra $S_{\alpha}(\nu)$ fit progressively to $S_{\alpha_0}(\nu)$, with $\alpha_0 = (0^\circ, 0^\circ)$.

But as appears in expression (1), the spectral factorization of the power spectrum $H_{\alpha}(\nu)$ is required for deconvolution. However, for most shapes of the angular power density, no analytical expression of $H_{\alpha_0}(\nu)$ can be found, thus inducing two different means of implementation.

3.2. IMPLEMENTATION

Both ways of implementations have been detailed in [5]:

3.2.1. Exact deconvolution

The homomorphic cepstrum method is well known as a homomorphic signal processing technique and has been widely applied to deconvolution problems in various fields [8]. Here it has been used to get $H_{\alpha_0}(\nu)$ by numerical spectral factorization.

3.2.2. Approximated deconvolution

The relative error criterion (1) has been approximated to a criterion based on the power spectra. The idea is to neglect the information brought by the phase during the minimization. This leads to a mean square error between $\log[S_{\mathbf{h}}(\nu)]$ and $\log[S_{\alpha_0}(\nu)]$.

3.2.3. Selection of the order

The decision of the order forms a crucial point in the auto-regressive model fitting and remains as a most challenging subject of study for practical applications. Several selection methods have been proposed for finite auto-regressive process for example, the final prediction error method proposed by Akaike (1970). As most order selection criteria, it is a transformation of the residual variance $\hat{\sigma}_{\xi}^2(k)$, which is computed as a function of the order in model estimation k .

$$AIC(k) = N \cdot \log[\hat{\sigma}_{\xi}^2(k)] + 2k$$

The transformation is used as an attempt to deal with residual variance and prediction error. Indeed, in model estimation, the variance of the residuals always decreases by introducing more parameters, whereas the errors of prediction increases above the best order.

3.3. SIMULATION RESULTS

Let's consider a 10-sensors uniform linear array with half-wavelength spacing. The received signal consists in $Q=300$ components with random amplitudes and phases. The nominal DOA is 0° relative to array broadside, while the angular spread is varied from 1° to 9° . The number of snapshots is $T=100$ and the RMS values are based on 300 independent Monte Carlo experiments. The signal to noise ratio is 10 dB. In this ID case, simulations show that the deconvolution performances weakly depend on the prediction order, that's why we have chosen to work with a given order. In figure 2, it has been taken equal to 2, given by the Akaike criterion.

The performances of our algorithms are compared to MUSIC, Tuft-Kumaresan, Maximum Likelihood and Cramer Rao Bound. The Cramer Rao Bound has been calculated by the inversion of the Fisher information matrix.

$$[\mathbf{FIM}]_{i,j} = T \cdot \text{trace} \left(\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}}}{\partial \Psi_i} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{x}}}{\partial \Psi_j} \right)$$

The calculus in the ID case was first established in [6].

It appears that both deconvolution algorithms outperform subspace-based methods and moreover return a good estimation of the angular spreading. They provide satisfying results compared to the Cramer Rao bound. It also appears that the phase information loss due to the approximation doesn't induce any performance degradation.

Figure 2: Performances of the deconvolution in the stationary case

4. EXTENSION TO THE NON STATIONNARY CASE

In the case of non stationary signals, Linear Prediction methods can not raise again on the Wold representation and the auto-regressive model [7] to justify that a predictor can provide an optimal estimation. Now, with correlated diffuse paths, the array output no more presents spatial properties of stationarity and the Linear Prediction has to be extended.

4.1. SPATIAL SMOOTHING

The first idea to rectify the covariance matrix by a spatial smoothing and then to apply the deconvolution method used in the stationary case. But such technique won't provide consistent estimates. Indeed, the use of spatial smoothing is in fact forbidden by the non stationarity.

4.2. EXTENDED CRITERION

The idea is then to make the average of discriminant functions attributed to each sub-array of length equal to the predictor's rank:

$$f(\theta) = \sum_i |f_i(\theta)|^2 = \sum_i |a_i(\theta) \cdot b_i|^2$$

where b_i , the rejector, belongs to the noise subspace. In absence of noise, if the number N of sensors is strictly higher than the dimension of the signal subspace $\dim(E_s)$, i.e. $N > \dim(E_s) + 1$, the problem of minimal prediction error is undetermined. It is then interesting to retain the solution $b_{\min}$ of minimal norm, which provides the smallest variance of perturbation ($\propto |b_i|^2$). It is moreover easy to show that $b_{\min} \propto \Pi_b \cdot e$, where Π_b is the projector onto the noise subspace and $e = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ (length N). $b_{\min}$ is precisely the vector used in the Tuft-Kumaresan method [9]. The link between Linear Prediction and subspace-based methods is so enlightened.

Figure 3: Performance of the deconvolution in the non stationary case

4.3. SIMULATION RESULTS

Given that we consider small angular spreads, the simulation results represented in figure 3 have been obtained by a spatial smoothing. The simulation parameters used are identical to those taken in 3.3. except that the angular shape of the component signals are selected from a deterministic Gaussian distribution with mean equal to the nominal DOA. The order has also been kept constant during the angular spreading increasment. But contrary to the stationary case, the choice of the optimal order has a notable incidence on performances and highly depends on the angular spreading. This explains why the root mean square error of spreading estimate is not really satisfying, especially with the phase information loss.

But as far as DOA estimation is concerned, our deconvolution algorithms also outperform subspace-based methods in this most delicate case, that is to say, with coherently distributed sources. Besides, they provide satisfying results compared to the Cramer Rao Bound.

5. CONCLUSION

What is brought home to us is that, given that Linear Prediction methods can be efficiently extended to non stationary spatial series, they can be used for the characterization of distributed sources. This property has been exploited to implement a deconvolution process returning the direction of arrival and angular spreading of distributed sources with better performances than conventional subspace-based methods. However, the main problem remains the determination of the predictor's rank: this is an open question that is a matter of future research to improve our algorithms.

6. REFERENCES

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